

ISSUES OF YOUNG PEOPLE BELONGING TO THE SOCIAL RISK

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of young people in the social risk group and foreign experience in eliminating them. In particular, improving the activities of state and non-state actors in the prevention of offenses among minors and young people in the social risk group involves studying the experience of foreign law enforcement agencies. Practice shows that many countries very effectively use various forms and methods of preventive work with minors.

Keywords: criminal police, teenager, prevention of offenses, preventive work, National Council, public order, security police.

Today, in the conditions of complex and rapidly changing globalization in the world, the implementation of an effective state policy in the field of solving youth problems and the improvement of the mechanisms and technologies used in it remain one of the important factors in ensuring not only social stability, but also state security in general. It is relevant to study this issue from the perspective of the implementation of the tasks set by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On State Policy on Youth", Decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Government resolutions, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, the "Youth Strategy" until 2030, the Global Action Program for the Interests of Youth, and the videoconference meeting held under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of Work in the Field of Youth Policy and Further Improve the System of Working with Them" on April 11, 2023. Today, along with the large-scale work being carried out to solve pressing issues related to youth, problematic issues that await resolution in the field also remain.

In particular, the lack of understanding of the essence of the complex geopolitical and ideological processes taking place in the world among most young

people, the lack of a unified approach, concepts and ideas in this regard, in the face of the diversity of opinions that are consistent with the spirituality of our country, has made it increasingly urgent to combat various dangers and threats such as terrorism, religious extremism, fanaticism, separatism, human trafficking, "mass culture", and drug trafficking. It is important to prevent such negative situations among young people, to increase the effectiveness of preventive work aimed at sharply reducing delinquency and crime; to increase the activity of young people in the socio-political processes taking place in our country, to form a sense of involvement in reforms in them.

For the Republic of Uzbekistan, the youth issue is one of the priority areas of domestic and foreign policy. Despite the large-scale work being carried out in our country to radically improve all conditions for our people and their effective results, there are many cases of indifference, crime, and, worst of all, abandonment of our country and seeking happiness in other countries among young people, especially unorganized youth. This calls us to be vigilant and vigilant, and requires us all to work together on the youth issue and find a solution as soon as possible. However, in practical life, it can be seen that not all young people are covered by the attention of the state and the care of society. This situation was discussed by the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his speech at the IV Congress of the Kamolot Youth Social Movement: "...thousands of young people in our country, especially in rural areas, are being ignored not only by Kamolot, but also by the state and society. Almost no one is engaged in them, we would be admitting the bitter truth if we say that they are abandoned to their own devices. As a result, the number of unorganized young people, that is, those who do not work, do not study, do not have a specific occupation, and are exposed to negative influences, is increasing" [1].

Currently, 64 percent of the population of Uzbekistan is made up of young people under the age of thirty, and the share of this group has increased by 4 percent over the years of independence. The fact that Uzbekistan is the country with the largest population and a large percentage of children and young people in a geostrategically complex region like Central Asia requires us to set important tasks for the future from a political and demographic point of view.

Today, for Uzbekistan, which is implementing fundamental reforms on the basis of the Strategy of Actions in five priority areas of development, solving youth problems is becoming a matter of life and death. In this regard, it is urgent to scientifically and theoretically analyze and study the issue of "unorganized youth",

which is an important, integral component of strategic importance, which determines the level of development of the state and society, has a positive or negative impact on socio-economic growth [2, 192].

Improving the activities of state and non-state actors in preventing crimes among minors and young people belonging to socially at-risk groups involves studying the experience of foreign law enforcement agencies. Practice shows that many countries use various forms and methods of preventive work with minors very effectively.

The legal education program developed by the law enforcement agencies of the state of Florida, USA, and implemented in most public and private schools is noteworthy. The main task of the program, designed for students in grades 7-8, is to familiarize minors with the system of values existing in society, the basics of criminal law and the obligations of a citizen, as well as to form ideas about what awaits violators of law and order. Using a question-and-answer format, the program introduces students to the laws related to offenses such as robbery, trespassing, vandalism, resisting arrest, illegal possession of weapons, shoplifting, arson, alcohol, illegal drug use, and murder. Separate chapters examine the consequences of criminal activity, as well as the need for laws and special bodies to monitor their implementation in society.

The educational material is embodied in a 135-page textbook, and a special book has even been developed for teachers. Specially invited police officers are widely used to explain each law being studied in detail. This not only increases interest in the material being studied, but also serves as a powerful moral factor. Students learn to see police officers as people who sympathize with them and care about their well-being [3, 18].

An unusual experiment is being tested in the Los Angeles Police Department (USA), namely the effectiveness of a program to prevent delinquency among adolescents in correctional institutions. The purpose of this program is to have a psychological impact on adolescents who have not yet committed a crime, but are registered with the internal affairs bodies for criminal tendencies, drug addiction or antisocial behavior.

The experience of the police in preventing juvenile crime in Germany is considered instructive. In particular, the strategy for combating juvenile crime in Germany is based on the following principles: the tendency of adolescents to commit illegal acts in most cases disappears without any external influence after the

completion of the process of personality formation; strict measures by state authorities often lead to negative consequences. In North Rhine-Westphalia, special commissions have been established in all major police departments to investigate drugs, missing persons and juvenile crimes, and the commissioners are tasked with analyzing cases in which adolescents are often involved as perpetrators, victims or witnesses. Control and general coordination of work with adolescents are carried out by the leadership of the internal affairs department. A special database on juvenile offenses has been created in the information system of the criminal police department, and based on the data entered into it, the causes and characteristics of the development of juvenile delinquency are analyzed. The results of such studies are used in the education, training and retraining of internal affairs officers [4, 24].

In Baden-Württemberg, the major criminal police departments have special departments for juvenile offenders, while other services are staffed exclusively with juvenile delinquents. The tasks of the special departments and staff are focused on analyzing all cases in which juveniles act not only as perpetrators, but also as victims or witnesses. In the state of Bremen, there are special services for juveniles within the criminal and security police. The tasks of these services are clearly defined, and while the special security police services are responsible for preventing juvenile delinquency, the police are responsible for investigating offenses committed by children and adolescents. In Lower Saxony, the police work closely with other social services in handling cases of juvenile delinquency. In Berlin, a much higher level of organization has been achieved in working with juvenile delinquents. To work with adolescents, a special commission has been established within the internal affairs department, which takes action on all reports and reports on offenses committed by children and adolescents, as well as on applications for missing minors. The commission's employees not only investigate these cases, but also carry out preventive work. The experience of police activities in other European countries is also very interesting.

In the process of research, foreign experience is analyzed in a comparative manner with the experience of Uzbekistan, and person-oriented methods are used. Analysis of the practice of functionally specialized entities aimed at preventing juvenile delinquency abroad allows us to identify three main areas of this work: the first area - the creation of a legal framework for the activities of juvenile justice bodies, the introduction of new social technologies, socio-legal structures and non-

governmental structures, and, in a number of Western countries, this experience was introduced a long time ago and has existed for many years, over time proving not only its viability, but also its absolute necessity; the second area is related to the organization of specialized courts, which play the main organizational and coordinating role in the system of preventing juvenile delinquency, which are the core of juvenile justice; the third area is the formation of special preventive entities, including the structure of police bodies, and the assignment of humanistic functions to them.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, when working with young people who are at social risk, it is advisable to organize business trips to the regions, meet directly with young people who have spiritual and moral problems, children from troubled families, who are prone to crime or are on preventive lists, conduct educational activities during the trips, collect questionnaires, analyze the results obtained through them, and prepare methodological guidelines based on the results of the research.

These activities will contribute to the improvement of the system of individual work with young people who have spiritual and moral problems, children from troubled families, who are prone to crime or are on preventive lists. Measures aimed at solving the problems of unorganized and problematic young people will help them to gain confidence in their future and self-confidence. Through questionnaires, urgent problems among young people in the regions are identified and analyzed. The education of problematic youth is facilitated by the instillation of the idea of “Serving and being loyal to the development of the Motherland”. They are directed towards a comprehensive educational approach aimed at harmonizing personal and national interests. At the same time, it serves to form a person with high moral qualities, capable of fighting for the honor and dignity of the country, with strong spiritual immunity, hardworking, and strong faith.

In our country, it is also important to educate young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, to ensure their scientific and professional development, health, expansion of economic opportunities, employment, training them in modern professions, involvement in sports, working with young people abroad, and strengthening national and family values.

It is a requirement of the time to solve such tasks as creating decent working conditions for young people, protecting their legal rights related to labor, comprehensively supporting unorganized youth by expanding their economic rights

and opportunities, meaningfully organizing their free time, further improving the system of wide involvement in sports, educating young people in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, family, ideas of independence, respect for national and universal values, ensuring security, environmental stability, justice and equality in the country, and increasing the role of young people in preventing crime and delinquency, developing state youth policy based on international standards, working with compatriots abroad, including youth, and strengthening cooperation with international youth organizations.

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